

Assessment on Regulation of... DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10697841>

Assessment on Regulation of Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) on Teachers' Attitude towards Students Behaviour Disposition

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Abstract

This study assessed the regulation of teacher's registration council of Nigeria and teachers' attitude towards student's behaviour disposition. The authors adopted episode conceptual method and inferential statistics. The population consists of 601 teachers that came for 2019/2020 in-service training in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Sample and sampling techniques was used in selecting the sample size for the study. The instrument for the study was a questionnaire tagged ARTCATA structured along 2 points Likert scale. Data collected was analysed using percentage and ANOVA. The findings revealed that most teachers in Kaduna State have negative attitude towards TRCN and this invariably affects behaviour disposition. The paper concludes that motivation determine what teachers do and attitudes determine how well they do their tasks.

Keywords: TRCN, behaviours, regulatory council, discipline

Introduction

Generally, good behavior among secondary school students could be achieved by setting a high positive standard of attitudes by the teachers and executing strong disciplinary control measures over it. Teachers form the bedrock on which the whole of the school activities are built. Consequently, once their attitude is not favourable towards their Regulatory Council, the whole objectives of teaching and learning become defective. Teacher's attitudes towards the TRCN are relevantly significant to the school system because it affects the role of the teacher and his/her teaching methodology, mastering of lessons and good behaviours which in turn affect the students' general behaviour. We cannot keep on complaining about Nigerian problems while we do nothing on her future. The kind of education that lacks discipline will definitely produce graduates that lack integrity and morals. If teachers are not having positive attitudes towards their regulatory body (TRCN), it then means that they are rebellious to anything good for National Development. They will replicate themselves to their young learners and the vicious cycle of indiscipline and corruption continue. One wonders therefore, whether teachers of today will have such moral strength to defend their professional integrity. These have occasioned conflicts and controversies and have misled many into opposing teaching as a profession. It was in the light of these facts that the Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT) on several occasion embarked on an exceptional strike demanding among other things the establishment of Teacher's Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) as a regulatory body for the teaching profession. On 21st August 2002, the Council was inaugurated and registration of teachers began in earnest in 2005. Presently, more than 700,000 teachers according to TRCN statistical digest (2021) have responded positively in terms of registration. However, the Council noted that poor attitudes of teachers and students, poor educational culture and character and lack of good behaviour among students and teachers arc the cause of acute falling standard of education in Nigeria. This was confirmed by 2019 WAEC record which revealed that out of 1.5 million candidates that sat for the May/June 2019 WAEC examination, only 472,906 candidates obtained five credits and above including English and Mathematics. These, if not well controlled may mar the National efforts to meet education for all (EFA)

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made at Jomtien (Thailand) and reconfirmed in Dakar 22 years later. The position of this research is therefore not for the Council to take the erring teachers to Court, rather is concerned with mechanisms, procedures, managerial and organizational processes to reduce opportunities for teachers to hold poor attitudes towards TRCN as regards to students' behaviour and to redirect the erring ones into positive attitudes. It will also provide to the council key tools that will identify "red flags" that /can help to detect risks of attitudes of teachers. This is because teachers are meant to make a positive change in the lives of their students. To guide this study therefore, four research questions were raised, three questions were answered while one question was hypothesized and was tested at 0.05 level of significance. A functionalist theorist, Katz (2011) proposed that attitude is determined by the functions they serve. According to him, people hold given attitudes because it helps them to attain their basic goals. He developed four types of functions that attitudes meet. They are as follows:

1. Instrumental: People develop positive attitudes towards things that aid or reward them. They want to maximize reward and minimize penalties. People develop attitudes that help them meet these goals.
2. Knowledge: Attitudes help in supplying people with evaluation.
3. Value-Expression: Professional workers adopt certain beliefs and values that guide their way of life.
4. Ego-Difference: Attitude acts as defensive mechanism on the working group. Those with feelings of inferiority may develop attitude of superiority.

According to this theorist, attitude change the teachers towards TRCN. It may be negative when the TRCN no longer serves its function and so teachers feel frustrated. On the other hand, Gimba (2020) opined that attitude is a persistent tendency to feel and behave in favourable or unfavourable ways towards the attitude object (i.e. TRCN). Attitudes may have both good and bad elements. Teachers are the attitude holders while TRCN is the attitude object in this context. In every organization, managers are concerned about employee's attitudes. This is because; attitudes are the major causes of employees work behaviour. Positive attitudes according to Katz (2011) always leads to productivity efforts, whereas negative ones lead to poor work habit and so TRCN as the teachers' Regulatory Body needs to know this facts. Katz still maintained that when one has favourable attitudes, one intends to promote the interest and welfare of the object while someone with unfavourable attitude tends to somehow work against it. From the above concept, teachers' attitudes towards TRCN could mean teachers prevailing tendency to respond favourably or unfavourably towards TRCN Code of Professional Conduct.

It is important to note that misconducts are inevitable part of school as a system. This is because individuals working in the school system are of varied background and make-up. However, every system including school has goals to achieve. To unify these people with different threats, the TRCN has the followings as viable benchmarks in assessing teachers' attitudes towards the Council as regard to students' behaviours TRCN (2005). Respects for learners right and dignity. No child should suffer any form of discrimination. Responsibility to the educational programme. The council expects all students to learn and be directed towards excellence. The TRCN expects teachers to be focused and genuine active listener of their students.

1. Confidentiality: TRCN expects teachers to keep strictly secret concerning anything discovered from their students which when disclosed may hamper their social relationship or academic excellence.
2. Fair remuneration: This seems to be the sine qua non for personal regard. Unless students perceive the teacher as being fair in making decisions that affect them such as marking answer scripts, giving help, arbitrating in disputes, they cannot begin to love such teacher. This accounts why Johnson (2011) lamented that teachers often create classes of students - the "bright" and the "slow" and the "Have" and the "Have not". Student of course read these partial attitudes of teachers and consequently, they develop either high or poor self-image resulting from high or low academic performance.
3. Sexual misconduct: Some teachers according to the TRCN (2010) indulge in sexual relationship with their students, which in most cases lead to favouritism in the form of giving marks than what they deserve and unwanted pregnancy.
4. Abuse of Office: According to Ilori (2000), students quickly learn a variety of new responses such as drug addiction and sexual harassment from their teachers. It is no more a secret that most teachers exploit their students through lesson fees and other illegal fees.
5. Examination Malpractices: According to Alutu (2016) teachers are the prime movers of this ugly trend. Each year, according to Ekejuiba (2010) most examination bodies cancel an average of 74,000 results on account of exam malpractice. An average of 450 principals and teachers are blacklisted for aiding it.
6. Patronage of illegal learners Group: It has been generally observed that some influential teachers successfully create

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factions with the students against their fellow teachers or school authorities. They mislead the students by discussing personalities and things that are not related to the students. Consequently, students display undesirable behaviour towards their authorities.

7. **Role Model:** The mode of some teachers dressing tends to reduce the image of teaching profession. Some female teachers wear tight shirt and transparent skirt while their male counterparts wear flowing gowns (baba-riga). Some wear dark glasses which are not in line with teachers dressing ethics. According to TRCN (2005), registered teachers cannot lay claim to be professionals if their conducts before students fall short of what is expected by the Council.
8. **Corrupt Practices:** There is general allegation that some teachers' violet this guideline through the following means:
 - a. **Bribery:** Teachers bribe their employees.
 - b. **Fraud:** Teachers according to the public has become a mill where GCE, WAEC and NECO question papers are created.
 - c. Existence of ghost teachers on pay-rolls.
 - d. Favouritism.
 - e. **Nepotism:** Some teachers give priority to their children and family members.
 - f. **Illegal collection of fees:** These teachers do them through sales of handouts, extra-lesson and handworks.
 - g. **Corporal punishment:** In our contemporary society, the administration of corporal punishment by school teachers has led to "loss of lives and permanent injury" (Peretomode, 1993). This is an outright violation of human rights (FRN, 1999).
 - h. **Discipline:** TRCN under this guideline expects the teachers to administer these disciplinary exercises in accordance with school rules and regulation and with strict adherence to human right law.
 - i. **Ideological influence:** The council expects the teachers not to influence the students in whatever form and not to involve them in any of their political, social or religious idiosyncrasies.

Within a given organization, each person develops a distinctive pattern of traits that characterized his or her social conducts. This stable response disposition according to Katz (2011) channels the behaviour of individual within an organization. Thus, the way a teacher complies with the council's code of conduct is determined by his attitude to it. It is not surprising therefore; those teachers' attitudes towards TRCN affect their working situation. With the author's experiences as desk officers of TRCN and through teachers/public opinions, it was discovered that the following factors influence teachers' attitudes towards the council.

Some teachers run illegal schools where they manufacture answers to any questions. Students in turn have strong hope in these centers and hardly work for any exams. This is against TRCN (2005) (5) Code of conducts. According to functionalist theorist Katz (2010), attitudes develop in the process of want satisfaction. In trying to cope with daily problems to satisfy their basic needs, teachers develop attitudes. For instance, Gowon (2005) lamented that lack of indiscipline among teachers resulting to lateness to school; absenteeism and divided loyalty are the major factors that affect students' moral and academic excellence. This is against the expectation of TRCN even when teachers' wants such as recognition, promotion, professional salary scale and training are met.

The attitudes of teachers towards TRCN are shaped by the information to which they are exposed. Communication is seen as a process of sharing opinions and ideas openly and freely being mindful of others' views. Since some teachers especially in private schools are not sufficiently informed on TRCN expectations, they do not want to change the behaviour of truant students. Thus, making them to become frustrated, resentful and resort to act of indiscipline which is against TRCN Code of Conduct (2005). And as long as suspicions prevail among some teachers in the private schools about TRCN, problem is bound to erupt. Many of the attitudes of the individual teacher have their source and their support in the groups to which the individual gives his/her allegiance. In some schools as observed by these researchers, for teachers to maintain their unfavourable attitudes towards the TRCN, they must have support of likeminded persons. If such teachers cannot find or form informal groups which hold negative view towards the council to their own, they collapse into positive attitudes and comply accordingly. Some others seek out informal groups in which the prevailing attitudes are congenial and turn to propaganda

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which support their established negative attitudes. Such kind of attitudes makes students to create faction among themselves and rebel against school authorities. Poor working condition causes teachers' attrition rather than attraction. When this happens students quickly learn a variety of new responses like aggression and drug addiction.

There have been some counterfeit agencies that collect illegal money from the teachers. Some of these agencies which emanate under the umbrella of NUT officials were exposed. Nation' Tuesday July 21st 2019, which had the caption "Nigeria teachers union officials face trials over alleged seventy- three-million-naira scam. The detail of the story reveals that some officials of NUT in Narrageve and Fika Local Government Area of Yobe State are standing trial before a Senior Magistrate Court in Potiskun for allegedly collecting a loan of N73.5 million (NUT, Money) from Bank with the aim of purchasing motor cycle for teachers on hire purchase. The accused NUT officials bought motor cycles worth of N33 million and embezzled the rest alongside with other reported illegal money collected from teachers in the name of their welfare and they were asked to pay back the money. This act of fraud equally makes the teachers to exploit the students with different illegal fees.

Research Objectives

The aim of the study is to examine the assessment on regulation of Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) and teachers' attitude towards students' behaviour disposition. The specific objective of the study is to;

1. examine the attitudes of teachers towards students' behaviour disposition
2. determine how teachers' attitudes has affects students' behaviours disposition
3. investigate the factors that influence teachers' attitudes towards students' behaviour disposition

Research Questions

1. What are the attitudes of teachers towards students' behaviour disposition?
2. Do teachers' attitudes affect students' behaviours disposition?
3. What are the factors that influence teachers' attitudes towards students' behaviour disposition?

Hypothesis 1:

Ho₁: There are no significant differences among the factors that influence teachers' attitudes towards students' behaviour disposition.

Methodology

The researchers employed a comprehensive and systematic episodic conceptual approach, utilizing a series of in-depth literature reviews to elucidate and advance the understanding of teachers' attitudes towards the Teachers' Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN). This method was particularly chosen to delve into the intricacies of teacher attitudes in relation to the expectations outlined by TRCN, as well as their attitudes towards students, incorporating inferential statistics for a more nuanced analysis. In order to capture a representative sample for the study, a meticulous sample and sampling technique were employed, resulting in the selection of 120 participants. The researchers judiciously chose this sample size to ensure the robustness and reliability of their findings. To gauge the multifaceted aspects of teachers' attitudes, the researchers designed a meticulously crafted questionnaire labeled as the Attitudes towards TRCN Assessment (ARTCATA). This instrument employed a structured format, utilizing a 2-point Likert scale to allow for a nuanced exploration of teachers' perspectives and sentiments.

In the subsequent phase of the research, the amassed data underwent a thorough analysis employing both quantitative and statistical methods. Percentages were employed to provide a descriptive overview of the data, offering insights into the prevalence and distribution of various attitudes among the participants. To unravel more intricate patterns and relationships within the data, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed, bringing a sophisticated statistical lens to the investigation. This methodological framework, blending conceptual depth, meticulous sampling, and advanced statistical analyses, contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay between teacher attitudes, TRCN expectations, and the dynamics of teacher-student relationships.

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Result

Research Question 1

What are the attitude of teachers towards student's behaviour disposition?

Table 1: Attitude of teachers towards TRCN in relation to students

S/N	ATTITUDES	AGGREE	DISAGREE
1	Respect student's right	31	69
2	Committed to the teaching and learning program	50	50
3	Empathy	57	43
4	Confidential	56	44
5	Fair to all students	63	37
6	Sexual misconduct	67	33
7	Examination Malpractice	59	41
8	Abuse of office	61	39
9	Patronage of illegal learners	52	48
10	Role model	43	57

Source: Field Survey 2023

Based on the numerical evidence in table 1, it could be held that though some teachers have positive attitudes towards TRCN, majority of them have negative attitudes towards TRCN in the following ways: disrespect for student's right [69%], Sexual misconduct [67%], Examination Malpractices [59%], Abuse of Office [61 %],[Patronage of illegal Learners Group[52%], and poor role Model [57%] .The findings were in accordance with the conclusion of Wokocho [2011], the findings of Alutu [2006] and Ekejiuba [2010]. The implication of these findings was that the students would not be open to teachers because of fears of unknown and therefore unable to learn.

Research Question 2

Do teachers' attitude affect students' behaviours disposition?

Seventy two percent (72%) of teachers agreed that teachers' attitudes affect student's behaviour. This finding was in line with the theory of Katz (2010). This implied that most students behave as they are made to be behaved by their teachers. They could either be affected positively or negatively depending on the actions and inactions of their teachers

Research Question 3

What are the factors that influence teachers' attitudes towards students' behaviour disposition?

Table 2: factors that affect teachers' attitudes towards TRCN

S/N	FACTORS	Agreed	Disagreed
1	Special/Miracle Centers	43	57
2	Individual Teachers Wants	31	69
3	Inadequate information from TRCN	64	36
4	The informal group Affiliations	63	37
5	Poor working condition	87	13
6	Past experience / teacher's perception about the Council and NUT	66	34

Source: Field Survey 2023

The findings in table 2 revealed that certain factors such as inadequate information from TRCN (64%), the informal GROUP AFFILIATIONS (63%), poor working condition (87%) and past experience/teacher's perception about the Council and NUT (66%) were believed to affect teachers' attitude towards TRCN negatively more than other factors. These findings were not in favour of TRCN (2005), (5) and (13) professional code of conduct. These implied that poor standard of education, communication gap, lack of teachers' motivation and transfer aggression did exist in the educational system on account of these factors. These account for noncompliance with TRCN with according to TRCN (2005) and Katz (2011) affect students'

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academic performance and behaviours negatively.

Hypothesis 1

There are no significant differences among the factors that influence teachers’ perception towards students’ behaviour disposition

Table 3: the ANOVA test of significant differences among the factors that influence teachers’ attitudes towards students’ behaviour disposition:

Part C	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sign
Between groups	110.281	6			
Within groups	548.900	763	18.380	25.549	.000
Total	659.181	769			

Table 3 shows significant differences among the factors that influence attitudes towards TRCN. This is because the mean square indicated that were differences in the level at which the factors significantly influence teachers’ attitudes TRCN. However, it was not clear at his stage if the differences were between only two series or/and all the six series. To determine this, the authors made use of the tabulate command (i.e Post Hoc Test) with the summarized option, as shown in table 4.

Table 4: Post Hoc Tests: Means of Group in the Homogeneous sub set displayed

Ducan	Subset (means) for alpha 0.05			
	N	1	2	3
Factors				
Special / Miracle Centers	110	2.27		
The informal group Affiliation	110		2.58	
Individual Teachers wants	110			
Inadequate information from TRCN	110			
Teachers perception bout NUT	110			
Poor working condition				
Sign		0.691	.150	1.00

Table 4 indicates that there is significant differences among the factors that influence teachers’ attitudes towards student’s behaviour disposition.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study have bearing with the 601 teachers that came for 2019/2020 in-service training in Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. The null hypothesis which states that there are no significant difference among the factors that influence teacher’s perception towards students’ disposition which is in line with Gimba (2020) who posits that TRCN expects teachers to keep strictly secret concerning anything discovered from their students which when disclosed may hamper their social relationship or academic excellence and Johnson (2011) lamented that teachers often create classes of students - the “bright” and the “slow” and the “Have” and the “Have not’. Student of course read these partial attitudes of teachers and consequently, they develop either high or poor self-image resulting from high or low academic performance.

The finding on Teachers' Attitudes towards Students' Behavior Disposition reveals a concerning landscape of teachers' attitudes towards students. While some teachers exhibit positive attitudes, a majority display negative attitudes in critical areas. For instance, 69% of teachers disagree with respecting students' rights, and 67% are in disagreement with the prohibition of sexual misconduct. These findings are consistent with previous research by Gowon (2015), which has also highlighted issues related to teachers' attitudes.

The finding on The Influence of Teachers' Attitudes on Students' Behavior suggests that 72% of teachers agree that their attitudes affect students' behavior. This finding aligns with the conclusion of Johnson (2010), which emphasizes the strong influence teachers have on their students. Students often model their behavior based on their teachers' actions and attitudes. Therefore, teachers' positive attitudes can inspire and motivate students, while negative attitudes can discourage and potentially lead to poor behavior.

The finding on Factors Influencing Teachers' Attitudes towards Students' Behavior Disposition highlights several factors that influence teachers' attitudes towards the Teaching Regulatory Council of Nigeria (TRCN) and, by extension,

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students' behavior. Inadequate information from TRCN, informal group affiliations, poor working conditions, and past experiences significantly affect teachers' attitudes negatively, according to the findings. These factors agree with TRCN (2005) potentially leading to issues in the education system.

Conclusion

Motivation determines what teachers do and attitudes determine how well they do their tasks. Ability is what teachers are capable of doing, motivations determine what they do, and attitudes determine how well they do their tasks. There is no substitute for teachers who are dedicated to their nation and students. The future of the nation rests in the hands of its teachers. The moral qualities of teachers today will inevitably be reflected in the citizens of tomorrow. In spite of the TRCN giant stride on teachers' welfare, there persists a worrisome dwindling demand for teachers' progress and commitments. There are many compelling reasons why teachers' attitudes are not in congruent with TRCN Code of Conduct on students' behaviour. If good behaviours are not inculcated to students by teachers, to wipe away robbery, militant groups, kidnapper and all kinds of anti-social acts will be a mirage in Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. TRCN should ensure that teachers are met at their different need disposition
2. TRCN should create a forum for dialogue and decision making with teachers' representatives over the matters that concern them.
3. Adequate control and monitoring measures by TRCN should be put in place for teachers.
4. Teachers should avoid all misconduct that are threats to good school climate and could affect the students.

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